

The Strategic Role of HRM and Managing Human Resources in Era 4.0

Andrea Gideon
gideon8850@gmail.com

Lena Ellitan
lena@ukwms.ac.id

Faculty of Business, Widya Mandala Catholic University Surabaya, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

This article aims to explore the role of strategic HR management in managing employees in Era 4.0. By using a literature review approach and qualitative descriptive methods, this research uses changes in HR management as a response to rapid technological transformation. The results of this research show that developing employee competency, applying technology in HR management, workplace flexibility and technology-based leadership development are the main focuses of strategic HR management in Era 4.0. In the midst of rapid change, HR management must adapt to technological advances and lead cultural transformation. With the right approach, strategic HR management can create an inclusive work environment, productive of adaptive funds, improve organizational performance and better prepare human resources to face future challenges. The conclusion is that strategic HR management plays an important role in managing employees in Era 4.0, emphasizing employee skill development, application of technology, workplace flexibility and technology-based leadership development.

Keywords :Strategic HR, HR Management, Era 4.0

INTRODUCTION

Era 4.0, known as the Fourth Industrial Revolution, is a period of deep transformation marked by the integration of advanced digital technology into almost every aspect of human life. (Young et al., 2020). This involves the use of internet-based technology, artificial intelligence (AI), big data, robotics, and various other technologies that enable the collection, analysis, and utilization of data more efficiently and effectively (Hendriyadi, 2019). One of the main characteristics of Era 4.0 is extensive connectivity between devices, systems and humans through the Internet of Things (IoT). Examples can be found in various industries, such as the manufacturing industry which uses sensors to connect production machines and obtain real-time information about their performance and condition. As a result, companies can respond to problems quickly and make improvements to production efficiency (Lukasik & Stachowiak, 2020).

Furthermore, according to (Saniuk et al., 2020) artificial intelligence also plays an important role in Era 4.0 with its ability to process data quickly and analyze complex patterns. For example, in the financial services sector, banks utilize artificial intelligence

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systems to analyze customer behavior and provide more accurate recommendations regarding investments or other financial services. According to (Setiawati et al., 2022), the Fourth Industrial Revolution also creates new challenges and opportunities in the world of work. Robotics and automation are changing the workforce landscape by replacing some repetitive and routine jobs, while new jobs are emerging in areas such as data analysis, software development, and information technology management. However, while Era 4.0 promises tremendous advances in efficiency and productivity, it also raises new questions and concerns regarding data privacy, cybersecurity, and the socio-economic impact of job displacement due to automation. (Lima et al., 2023). Furthermore, according to (Park et al., 2020) Era 4.0 requires careful thinking and wise policies to ensure its benefits can be widely enjoyed and its negative impacts can be minimized.

Era 4.0 has significantly changed the landscape of workplaces and industries, influencing the way organizations operate and interact with employees. (Salimova et al., 2020). Rapid technological transformation has resulted in significant changes in the demands and expectations of the workforce. Companies must adapt quickly to remain competitive and take advantage of the opportunities offered by these changes. (Luz Tortorella et al., 2022). One of the main impacts of Industry 4.0 is increased automation and the use of artificial intelligence in production and administration processes. According to (Achouch et al., 2022) This causes changes in the type of work required, routine and repetitive work tends to be replaced by technology, while work that requires creativity, problem solving and interpersonal skills becomes more important. Therefore, management in Era 4.0 must be different from before. Managers must be facilitators of change and innovation, and have the ability to lead culturally and technologically diverse teams. They also need to understand new technologies and how to implement them effectively in business operations.

Furthermore, according to (Nopi Hidayat et al., 2022) strategic HR management is becoming increasingly important in Era 4.0. This includes employee development, data-based performance management, and the development of an innovative and collaborative work culture. Managers also need to pay attention to employee welfare and work-life balance to ensure that the workforce remains productive and happy in a rapidly changing work environment. Thus, Era 4.0 has changed the management paradigm in the workplace and industry. Managers need to understand and respond to rapid changes in technology and market demands, and have the ability to lead and manage employees in a dynamic and complex environment. Based on the background described above, the aim of this research is to determine the role of strategic HR management in employee management in the 4.0 era.

The Role of HRM and Development in Organizations

Human Resources (HR) plays an important role in managing employees in any organization. One of HR's main roles is to recruit and select the right employees for available positions (Stopochkin et al., 2022). This process involves determining organizational needs, preparing clear job descriptions, and selecting employees who have the skills, knowledge, and personality that match the company's needs (Tanga et al., 2022). Apart from recruitment, according to (Idrus et al., 2023) Human Resources (HR) is also responsible for developing existing employees through training and development programs. This includes providing training to improve employee skills and knowledge, as well as providing opportunities for career development and professional growth. By

ensuring employees continue to develop, HR helps increase employee motivation and performance, while meeting the organization's need for quality human resources.

Furthermore, according to (Oktarina et al., 2020) HRM also plays an important role in managing employee performance. This involves setting performance targets, providing feedback, and evaluating employee performance periodically. Through an effective performance management process, HRM helps ensure that employees remain focused on organizational goals, improve their performance, and identify areas that need improvement. In addition, HRM is also responsible for managing the relationship between employees and management. This includes handling workplace problems that may arise, such as conflicts between employees or issues related to employee welfare. Through a fair and open approach, HRM helps ensure workplace relationships remain harmonious and productive.

Lastly, HR also plays a role in ensuring compliance with employment-related regulations and policies. This includes ensuring that the organization complies with applicable employment laws and implements internal policies that are fair and aligned with best practices. By ensuring compliance, HRM helps protect the interests of employees and the organization as a whole (Zaky, 2020). In Era 4.0, the role of Human Resources (HR) in managing employees is experiencing significant changes in response to rapid technological transformation. In this context, HR is facing new challenges and unprecedented opportunities. One of the main changes is the widespread integration of digital technology in every aspect of HR management.

In Era 4.0, HR utilizes technology to support the employee recruitment and selection process. Digital platforms and artificial intelligence algorithms are used to reach potential candidates and enable deeper analysis of candidates that meet organizational needs. Apart from that, HR also utilizes data and analytics to manage employee performance, make decisions based on data, and identify career development trends. Furthermore, in Era 4.0, HR is also responsible for managing employees who are increasingly diverse in terms of culture, generation, and skills. This requires an approach that is inclusive and sensitive to individual needs and preferences, as well as developing a work culture that emphasizes diversity, inclusivity and collaboration. Strategic HR management in Era 4.0 also focuses on developing skills that are relevant to new technology and rapidly changing work environments. In Era 4.0, according to (Rahmat, 2021) HR also plays a role in managing employees who increasingly tend to work flexibly, such as freelance workers or remote workers. This requires changes to employee management policies and practices, including implementing technology that supports remote work and building trust between management and employees working outside the office.

Therefore, HR in Era 4.0 must strengthen skills in managing technology and data, leading cultural transformation, and creating a dynamic and inclusive work environment. By utilizing technology and innovation, HR can act as a catalyst for change, resulting in an organization that is adaptive, collaborative and competitive in the ever-changing digital era. Next, the role of strategic HR management in managing employees is in the Application of Technology in HR Management.

Developing employee competency is a key aspect in strategic HR management in Era 4.0. In the midst of rapid technological transformation, organizations need to ensure that their employees have the skills and knowledge relevant to today's needs. Digital literacy is one of the main competencies needed, considering that most jobs currently utilize information and communication technology (Marthalia, 2023a). For example, employees must be able to use software and digital platforms, manage data, and understand basic

concepts such as cyber security and data privacy. In addition, critical thinking is becoming an increasingly important skill in the 4.0 Era. Employees must be able to critically analyze information, evaluate various options and solutions, and make decisions based on evidence. For example, a manager must be able to understand the implications of technology new to business operations and consider the impact on overall company strategy.

The ability to adapt to technological changes is also key in developing employee competency in Era 4.0. Technology is developing rapidly, so employees must be able to learn and adapt to new technologies that emerge. For example, a software developer must be prepared to continuously update his skills in line with developments in programming and related technologies. By considering these aspects, strategic HR management can develop effective competency development programs to ensure that employees have the skills necessary for success in Era 4.0. This is not only beneficial for individual employees but also for the organization as a whole, as it can increase their competitiveness, innovation and adaptability in an ever-changing market.

Human resource development is an activity that must be carried out by organizations, so that their knowledge, abilities and skills are in line with the demands of the work they do. With this development activity, it is hoped that we can improve and overcome deficiencies in carrying out work better, in accordance with developments in science and technology used by the organization. Briefly, Muhadjir (1988) describes human resource development as improving human quality in physical and mental terms. Strategic human resource development is the development of a learning organization and the need for learning, development and training opportunities in order to improve individual, team and organizational performance.

Meanwhile, Walton's opinion in Sunarto (2005), explains that strategic human resource development includes introducing, eliminating, modifying, directing and guiding processes and responsibilities in a way where all individuals and teams are equipped with the skills, knowledge and competencies they need to carry out current and future tasks required by the organization. Human resource development is defined as the process of facilitating long-term work-related learning capacity at the individual, group and organizational levels through structured and unstructured learning and non-learning activities to improve organizational performance (Sunarsi, 2018). In addition, human resource development is the process of developing and releasing potential capabilities for the purpose of improving performance through organizational development and training and personnel development (Halton in Sunart, 2020).

The aim of strategic human resource development according to Sunarto (2005) is to produce a logically connected and comprehensive framework for developing people. Human resource development activities include learning and development, training programs, developing intellectuals and promoting organizational, team and individual learning. Focus on creating a learning organization in which knowledge is managed systematically. Human resource development is also about a planning approach to encourage self-development with adequate support and guidance from within the organization.

Application of Technology in HR Management

The application of technology in HR management is becoming important in this era 4.0, where information technology has become the backbone of modern business operations. One important aspect in applying technology in HR management is the use of a sophisticated HR management information system. This system allows companies to centrally manage employee data, from personal information to work history and training. For example, HRIS

(Human Resources Information System) allows organizations to automate HR administration processes such as attendance recording, leave management, and performance evaluation (David et al., 2023). Apart from that, technology also allows for more in-depth and measurable analysis of employee performance. By using data analysis tools such as big data and business intelligence, companies can analyze employee performance data to identify trends, patterns, and factors that influence productivity and performance. For example, by analyzing individual and team performance data, companies can identify high performers and design more effective employee development strategies.

Apart from that, the application of technology also makes it possible to provide services to employees more efficiently. For example, the use of a self-service portal or mobile app allows employees to access their personal information, request time off, and access training independently without having to go through complicated manual processes. This not only increases convenience for employees but also reduces the administrative burden for the HR department (Marthalia, 2023b). Therefore, the application of technology in HR management brings many benefits to companies, including operational efficiency, better employee understanding, and improved services for employees. By investing in information technology and sophisticated HR management systems, companies can strengthen their strategic HR management and prepare the organization to face the challenges and opportunities of Era 4.0.

Flexibility and Work Life Balance

In Era 4.0, where technology allows employees to connect from anywhere and at any time, work flexibility is important in increasing employee productivity and welfare. Strategic HR management must create a work environment that supports flexible work models, such as remote work, part-time work, or flexible scheduling. For example, technology companies such as Google and Microsoft have adopted flexible work policies that allow employees to work from any location of their choice, as long as they still achieve their expected results (Toyipur, 2020).

Furthermore, achieving balance between work and personal life is also a major concern in Era 4.0. Strategic HR management must ensure that employees have sufficient rest and recreation time outside of working hours, and avoid tiredness and exhaustion which can disrupt their health and performance. Examples of initiatives taken by some companies include flexible leave policies, health and wellness programs, and promotion of healthy lifestyles in the workplace.

Furthermore, according to (Nurhidayat et al., 2020) companies can also utilize technology to facilitate flexibility and work-life balance. For example, online collaboration applications and project management tools allow employees to work efficiently remotely, while time management tools can help them organize their work schedules according to personal needs. By facilitating work flexibility and work-life balance, companies can increase employee satisfaction and well-being, as well as increase their retention and productivity.

Therefore, strategic HR management must take proactive steps to create a work environment that supports flexibility and balance between employees' work and personal lives. In this way, companies can ensure employees remain productive, happy and committed to achieving company goals in the dynamic Era 4.0.

Leadership-based technological developments

Technology-based leadership development is very important in strategic HR management in Era 4.0. Effective leadership in a technology-influenced environment requires a deep understanding of the role of technology in work processes, as well as the ability to utilize it to achieve organizational goals. A technology-based leader must have

skills in managing virtual teams, using online collaboration tools, and facilitating effective communication between digitally connected team members. For example, CEOs of technology companies such as Elon Musk of Tesla or Satya Nadella of Microsoft have led organizational transformation by proactively leveraging technology to optimize operations and drive innovation (Istyanto & Nasrulloh, 2019).

Apart from that, technology-based leadership also requires the ability to encourage an innovative and collaborative work culture. A leader must be able to inspire creativity and innovation among team members, as well as create an environment that supports experimentation and the development of new ideas (Arwani, 2020). Strategic examples adopted by some companies include using online collaboration platforms to share ideas and provide incentives for employees who produce innovative solutions.

By considering these aspects, strategic HR management needs to invest in technology-based leadership development through special training and development programs. This can include training in technology management skills, transformational leadership and the development of an innovative culture. Through technology-based leadership, organizations can optimize the use of technology in their operations, strengthen competitiveness and prepare organizations to face the challenges and opportunities in Era 4.0

CONCLUSION

Based on this research, the role of strategic HR management in managing employees in Era 4.0 is very important. Developing employee competency, applying technology in HR management, workplace flexibility, and technology-based leadership development are the main focuses. Era 4.0 requires HR management to adapt to technological changes and lead the transformation of workplace culture. With the right approach, HR management can create an inclusive, productive and adaptive work environment. This will improve organizational performance and better prepare them to face future challenges. Improving the quality of human resources is very important, especially because Indonesia still lacks, let alone utilizing the latest technology. Technological sophistication cannot be negotiated in social life, let alone in the business world, and needs to be addressed maturely and on target. Because it is important to prepare human resources to have talents and skills. Improving human resources starts from education, training and guidance for human resources. In Industry 4.0, the basic capital that human resources must have is: skills, agility and culture, with different cultural backgrounds they can still work together.

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